

Survey of Millimeter-Wave Microstrip Patch Antenna Array for 5G Applications

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Abstract: Microstrip patch antenna array design is promising structure for advance communication applications. Array pattern is very hot research area among antenna researchers. Various combination of antenna array designs like 1X2, 2X2, 3X2, 2X3, 4X4 etc. are using in mobile phones and electronics applications. Upper range of Ka band which is more than 18GHz is known as mm wave. This paper studied about the various research works on millimeter-wave microstrip patch antenna array for 5G applications. Several antenna characteristics such as return loss, radiation pattern, bandwidth, directivity, antenna gain, radiation efficiency etc. are also studied.

Keywords: MM-wave, Microstrip, Antenna, Aarray.

1. INTRODUCTION

Microstrip patch antenna is a solitary layer structure which contains basically these four sections - Fix, Ground plane, Substrate and Taking care of part. It is exceptionally basic in development utilizing customary microstrip line feed. Fix can be given any shape however rectangular and round configurations are generally utilized. Ground Plane can be limited or vast as indicated by model (Transmission line - model, cavity model, full wave Model or method of minutes) utilized for investigation of measurements. Relative Permittivity and tallness are two significant attributes for substrate, Taking care of Part can be actualized in these manners - Microstrip line, coaxial test, Opening coupled and Vicinity coupled Feed. An Antenna is a basic segment in Radio correspondence framework that is required in both transmitting and accepting terminals. Each kind of antenna is acceptable in its own specific manner with various utilizations and properties. Microstrip fix antenna array is set of at least two fix components. Signs from the individual fix components are prepared so as to accomplish improved execution over single antenna. the recurrence assignment of 18 GHz to 86 GHz. Microstrip antenna is fundamental to help portable terminals of remote correspondence systems because of its light, smaller and integrated into the module circuit. Since the microstrip antenna is light, minimized and integrated into the module circuit, it is basic to help the versatile terminal of remote correspondence systems. To get highly order Examples, it is necessitated that fields from components of array are included emphatically wanted way and drop each other in different ways.

Figure 1: Basic structure of microstrip patch antenna array

New millimeter-wave and 5G remote standards are being proposed as an answer for the expanding demand for more bandwidth and higher information move rates. These high information rate objectives can be encouraged by wideband antenna arrays with wideangle pillar directing,

which can work with two symmetrical straight polarizations. The two polarizations can upgrade the limit and in this way can support the phantom proficiency of 5G correspondence joins. Bar controlling can be accomplished by two different ways, the utilization of stage shifters for every component of an array, by various sorts of beamforming systems, for example, Head servant framework, Blass network, Nolen grid, Rotman focal point, and so on. Stage shifters for millimeter-wave frequencies are very costly, limited band, and lossy. A beamforming system, then again, can maintain a strategic distance from these impediments. Steward grid is a generally utilized beamforming system, which comprises of standard components: 3-dB directional couplers, hybrids and postpone lines. A fix antenna can be utilized as a wideband component in an antenna array with expansive radiation design. A few structures of a solitary polarization, millimeter-wave antenna arrays with Steward lattice feed arrange have been portrayed in [6-8]. band fix antenna, and recreated VSWR and radiation designs for an antenna array.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

C. K. Ali et al.,[2019] Right now, is available a position of safety structure for double band microstrip patch antenna array that works at millimeter wave band with reverberation frequencies of 28 GHz, 24.9 GHz and bandwidths of 0.9 GHz, 0.3 GHz individually. The structure was mimicked by CST programming, where the pinnacle increase of 8.42 dBi is accomplished utilizing a little array antenna size of measurements "9mm* 8mm* 0.64mm" [Length*Width* Height]; this model can be a promising candidate for future 5G cell phones. Two arrangement of substrates materials have been examined and RO3210 has been chosen because of its great execution with this design.[1]

S. Kim, et al.,[2019] A 24 GHz Industrial, Logical, and Medical (ISM)- band Doppler radar antenna with high confinement is proposed for moving objective detecting applications. Both transmit (Tx) and get (Rx) antennas comprise of 2×2 microstrip patch antenna arrays. High disconnection of the proposed antenna is accomplished by embeddings intermittent Jerusalem cross space array between Tx port and Rx port, and therefore the surface wave from Tx port to Rx port is fundamentally stifled. The - 10 dB reflection coefficient bandwidth of the proposed antenna is 510 MHz, and the segregation between Tx port and Rx port is higher than 36.7 dB over the 24 GHz ISM band. The recreated half-power beamwidths are 58.53° for E-plane and 47.54° for H-plane. Test results show that high separation can prompt improve Doppler radar execution. The proposed antenna can be a decent candidate for sans contact monitoring of the pulse and respiration rate in social insurance applications.[2]

R. Babulkar et al.,[2019] In wireless communication, more than one signals are transmitted in the channel by using the concept of Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) which efficiently handles the inter symbol interference and utilizes the frequency and available bandwidth efficiently. Whereas for OFDM transmission technique is integrated with MIMO channel which contains multiple transmitter and receiver antenna at both ends.[3]

R. Tiwari, et al.,[2019] MIMO advancement has pulled in thought in remote correspondences, since it present gigantic augmentations in data throughput and association reach out without requiring extra transmission limit or transmit control, higher spooky viability and lessened obscuring, a few systems can be associated with improve the microstrip antenna move speed. Cluster design give more yield in UWb go so it will be relevant for LTE remote correspondence and 5G arrange. These consolidate introducing parasitic part either in coplanar or stack configuration, extending the substrate thickness and adjusting the condition of a patch by embeddings openings and examine new possible results of new wideband microstrip patch antenna for individuals to come.[4]

H. Khalili, et al.,[2018] This work presents another method of planning and executing minimal effort arrangement took care of microstrip antenna arrays with low sidelobe levels by applying standard single-layer PCB innovation. The method depends on the Z-parameter qualities acquired from the electromagnetic full-wave reproduction of the array components by utilizing a two-port system model. Two sorts of antenna arrays are structured and given the utilization of the proposed method. The main kind is a uniform straight array with sidelobe level of 24.2 dB at the 24.125 GHz recurrence band. The subsequent kind is a nonuniform straight array that gives at any rate half increasingly physical space between the focal patches to be utilized in 2-D arrays; this

antenna has sidelobe level of 25 dB at 24.125 GHz. The two antennas accomplish an incredible execution in the whole bandwidth of 250 MHz.[5]

K. Xing, et al.,[2017] A position of safety gap coupled patch antenna array with high front-to-back-ratio (FTBR) is planned at Q-band by utilizing substrate integrated coaxial line method, the inborn protected fenced in area of which is fit for building an equivalent stage and adequacy decreasing taking care of system with backlobe concealment. An illustrative case of a 6×6 patch antenna array is structured and manufactured with a 2×2 earlier check module by utilizing multilayer fluid gem polymer process. Estimated results demonstrate that the array can accomplish an increase of 17.6 dBi at 41.5 GHz and the first sidelobe levels is - 24.1 dB in the E-plane and - 20.4 dB in the H-plane. The comprehensive FTBR is better than 27 dB in both planes.[6]

T. Mikulasek et al.,[2013] A 2×2 microstrip patch antenna array took care of by a substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) taking care of system for 24-GHz radar applications is proposed right now. The microstrip patches are gap combined with the taking care of system comprising of an opposite cajole to-SIW progress and two Y-intersection power dividers. The antenna configuration is acted in the full-wave electromagnetic solver ANSYS HFSS and confirmed by estimation. At the operation recurrence 24 GHz, a created prototype has an addition of 11.1 dBi and a low sidelobe level underneath - 22 dB in the E-plane and - 33 dB in the H-plane.[7]

D. T. Pham, et al.,[2011] This work presents the improvement and portrayal of an ink-fly printed 2-piece, 1×4 phased-array antenna (PAA) framework on an adaptable Kapton polyimide substrate using carbon nanotube thin-film transistors (CNT-TFTs) as exchanging components in the stage moving system. A multilayer metal entomb association technique is utilized to create a total PAA framework with control lines. By properly controlling the ON and OFF conditions of different switches, a 4.99 GHz signal is guided from 0° to $- 27^\circ$, and the deliberate far-field radiation designs concur very well with the mimicked information. Twisting tests performed on the manufactured framework at bowing radii of 6.5 cm, 9.5 cm, 12 cm, and 24 cm additionally show great concurrence with the simulations.[8]

R. Bayderkhani et al.,[2010] A mix of spaces and arrangement took care of patch antenna array is acquainted driving with an array antenna with wide bandwidth, low sidelobe level (SLL), and high front-to-back ratio (F/B). Three structures are broke down. The main, the reference structure, is the ordinary arrangement took care of microstrip antenna array that works at 16.26 GHz with a bandwidth of 3%, SLL of - 24 dB, and F/B of 23 dB. The second is like the reference structure, yet a huge opening that covers the patch array is expelled starting from the earliest stage. This outcomes in a wide working bandwidth of over 72% for , with a 3 dB gain bandwidth of over 15.9%. The SLL of this structure is improved to more than at 16.26 GHz, and stable SLL of over 15.5-16.4 GHz band is additionally shown. This structure has a bi-directional radiation design. To make the example uni-directional and increment the F/B, a third structure is broke down.[9]

R. A. Alhalabi et al.,[2008] A high-productivity microstrip-took care of endfire calculated dipole antenna has been created for millimeter-wave phased array applications. The antenna is based on the two sides of a Teflon substrate ($\epsilon_{siv} r = 2.2$) and this permits a wideband feed from the single-finished microstrip line to the differential dipole. The structure brings about wide radiation designs for filtering purposes with an increase of around 2.5 dB at 20-26 GHz and a cross-polarization level of $< - 15$ dB at 24 GHz. A shared coupling of $< - 23$ dB is estimated between contiguous components with 6.8 mm community to focus separating (0.50-0.54 λ at 22-24 GHz). A variation of the calculated dipole antenna with an attractive ground plane edge was additionally evolved, and shows a deliberate increase of > 6 dB at 23.2-24.6 GHz and exceptionally low common coupling between components ($< - 23$ dB for a 6.8 mm separating). [10]

Table 1: Summary of literature survey

Sr No.	Author Name & Year	Proposed Work	Outcome
1	C. K. Ali, IEEE 2019	A low-profile design for dual-band microstrip patch antenna array resonance frequencies of 28 GHz, 24.9 GHz and bandwidths of 0.9 & 0.3 GHz.	A small array antenna size of dimensions “9mm* 8mm* 0.64mm” promising candidate for future 5G smartphones.

2	S. Kim, IEEE 2019	A 24 GHz Industrial, Scientific, and Medical band Doppler radar antenna with high isolation.	Half-power beam widths are 58.53° for E-plane and 47.54° for H-plane high isolation can lead to improve Doppler radar .
3	H. Khalili, IEEE 2018	A new of designing and implementing low-cost series-fed microstrip antenna arrays with low sidelobe levels.	This antenna has sidelobe level of 25 dB at 24.125 GHz. Both antennas the entire bandwidth of 250 MHz..
4	K. Xing, IEEE 2017	A low profile aperture-coupled patch antenna array with high FTBR is designed at Q-band by using substrate integrated coaxial line.	A gain of 17.6 dBi at 41.5 GHz and the first sidelobe levels is -24.1 dB in the E-plane and -20.4 dB in the H-plane.
5	T. Mikulasek IEEE 2013	A 2 × 2 microstrip patch antenna array fed by a SIW feeding network for 24-GHz radar applications.	A fabricated prototype has a gain of 11.1 dBi & low sidelobe level below -22 dB in E-plane and -33 dB in H-plane.
6	D. T. Pham, IEEE 2011	An ink-jet printed 2-bit, 1×4 PAA system on a flexible Kapton polyimide substrate utilizing CNT-TFT.	The fabricated system at bending radii of 6.5 cm, 9.5 cm, 12 cm, and 24 cm.
7	R. Bayderkhani, IEEE 2010	A combination of slots and series-fed patch antenna array array antenna with wide bandwidth, low SLL, and high ratio F/B.	A wide operating bandwidth of over 72% for , with a 3 dB gain bandwidth of over 15.9%.
8	R. A. Alhalabi , IEEE 2008	A high-efficiency microstrip-fed endfire angled-dipole antenna has been developed for millimeter-wave phased array.	A gain of around 2.5 dB at 20-26 GHz and a cross-polarization level of < -15 dB at 24 GHz.

3. CHALLENGES AND APPLICATIONS

3.1. Challenges

- Network traffic continues to grow rapidly; end-user performance demands continue to increase, straining the Radio Access Network (RAN) to deliver increased coverage, capacity and end-user throughput.
- This requires the wireless operators' networks to deliver gradually higher capacity over time. 5G New Radio (NR) enables new bands in the frequency range above 6 GHz, FR2, by adding flexibility and scalability in the numerology.
- For example, in the mmWave bands allocations at 18 GHz and 39 GHz, very wide operational bandwidths of the order of GHz are made available which support the need for capacity.
- The radio propagation is much more challenging at mmWave bands in comparison with lower bands in the range of 1-3 GHz carrier frequencies.
- To secure the reach of the mmWave signals, Advanced antenna system (AASs) play an important role to enable coverage via beamforming gain.
- AASs are enabling enhancements both for capacity and coverage. For lower bands, FR1 (below 6 GHz), the capacity enhancement is more essential due to the more interference limited environment. For the higher spectrum, FR2 (above 6 GHz), coverage enhancement is more essential due to the more challenging propagation and path loss conditions.

3.2. Applications

Microstrip patch antenna array is designed to increase the gain. The array antenna consists of two single patches on the same substrate.

Development of Proposed Antenna can be utilized for the following-

- Wi-Fi/Wi-max- Very high speed data access from internet.
- WLAN- Setup Wireless LAN.
- Automobiles- Driverless cars.
- Healthcare- Remote patient monitoring.
- Smart home- Home automation.
- Satellite communications band- For both uplink and downlink.

4. CONCLUSION

In addition to offering greater performance than LTE-Advanced, future networks must be much more energy efficient than current networks for 5G technology to be sustainable in the long term. Millimeter-wave (mmW) beamforming technology is a key enabling factor for the data capacity improvement that is essential for 5G networks to be commercially successful. Different combination of array is designing by researches for 5G network applications. Microstrip patch antenna array is promising design to meet requirement of 5G communication. This paper reviewed various previous design and performance enhancement in the field of antenna array. The demand of higher bandwidth and good gain can be achieved using array pattern antenna.

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